

An Electrometric Study of Uranyl-Salinazid Complex

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Received 3 March 1971

In continuation with our previous work¹, the present contribution describes a potentiometric and conductometric study of Uranyl-Salinazid system.

EXPERIMENTAL

AR grade chemicals were used. The 0.01M solution of salinazid has been prepared¹ in 95% ethanol.

An Elico LI-10 pH meter was used for pH measurements and Philips conductivity measuring bridge was used for conductometric studies.

The experimental procedure involved a series of pH and conductometric titrations of salinazid with standard NaOH in the absence and presence of uranyl ions at various salinazid to UO_2^{2+} ratios viz., 1 : 0, 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 in presence of 50% ethanol, keeping the total volume 25 ml. in each case. The readings were taken after 4 hr when equilibrium was established.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The Salinazid shows an increasing colour intensity with increase of pH, this may be due to enolisation² which can be represented by structures 'a' and 'b'.

In pH metric titrations, the lowered buffering region clearly indicates the release of H^+ ions during complex formation. The large shift in the position of the end point, clearly shows displacement of the proton due to complexation and the extent of proton displacement depends on the relative affinities of the ligand, for hydrogen ions and the metal ions. Since a considerable lowering in buffer regions is observed, the interaction of uranyl ion with salinazid is sufficiently great. The above facts along with the identical nature of curves when the molar ratios of uranyl : salinazid are 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 respectively, appear to indicate that formation of only 1 : 1 complex goes on according to the amount of alkali added. The two clear breaks at $a = 1$ and $a = 2$ can be represented by the following reactions :

The titration of salinazid alone clearly indicate that phenolic hydroxyl group is strongly hydrogen bonded and shows a break at $a = 1$. The higher pH in salinazid titration represents that owing to the increasing basicity³ of the hydrazone link, the phenolic proton is more strongly hydrogen bonded. The deepening in colour⁴ with increasing pH points out the enolisation of the $-CO-NH-$ group. This will make the oxygen atom to act as an electron donor, and hence the ligand will act as a tridentate ligand.

The conductometric study represents the change in conductivity when NaOH was added to salinazid, uranyl and their mixtures (i.e., 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3). The presence of a sharp break at $a = 2$ indicates a strong hydrogen bonding in the molecule.

The break at $a = 2$ confirms the process of enolisation as indicated by pH -metric titrations in presence of metal ions. This indicates the acidic nature of imino hydrogen^{5,6} as indicated in structure 1.

The conductometric study also favours the formation of only one complex in the ratio 1 : 1.

Thus the results of present study are in agreement with our earlier¹ results. Further it confirms the ionic nature of complex at low pH , but at higher pH the complex might be existing as a nonelectrolyte or in the form of its sodium salt. The various attempts to separate a solid complex could not succeed so far.

Our thanks are due to U.G.C. for providing financial assistance for this work.

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